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MOLECULAR VARIABILITY AND SEED TRANSMISSION OF GRAPEVINE RUPESTRIS STEM PITTING-ASSOCIATED VIRUS ISOLATES FROM SOUTHERN ITALY. M. Morelli¹, A. Minafra² and D. Boscia². ¹Dipartimento di Protezione delle Piante e Microbiologia Applicata, Università degli Studi, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, Unità Organizzativa di Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. E-mail: a.minafra@ba.ivr.cnr.it

Thirty-four *Vitis vinifera* accessions from southern Italy were tested for the presence of *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus* (GRSPaV), by Western blotting and RT-PCR (primer RSP48/RSP49). Due to the positive response of all samples, subsequent RT-PCR tests were done using three degenerate primer pairs, (GI, GII and GIII), designed in the CP region, for detecting putative molecular variants of GRSPaV. A very high percentage (94%) of the tested accessions were positive to GI used singularly (73%) or together with GII (18%), GIII (12%) or both (12%), whereas only a single infection was detected with GIII and none with GII. This suggests that at least three distinct molecular variants were found, of which GI is the most widespread, although mixed infections are also common. Fifteen PCR amplicons (RSP48/RSP49 fragments; 327bp) were sequenced and submitted to computer-assisted analysis. The sequences shared a nucleotide identity ranging from 90% to 100%. In phylogenetic trees constructed with our and GenBank sequences previously reported as "type strains", our isolates clustered in three different groups. In particular, four isolates grouped with GRSPaV (AF026278), one with GRSPaV-BS (AY881627) and ten with GRSPaV-SG1 (AY881626). Preliminary RT-PCR assays on GRSPaV transmission through pollen and seeds detected the virus in pollen collected from infected 110R rootstocks, but showed that it seems to be present on the outer surface rather than inside pollen grains.

FIRST REPORT OF AMERICAN PLUM LINE PATTERN VIRUS IN FLOWERING CHERRY IN ITALY. A. Myrta¹, J. Sanchez-Navarro², O. Potere³, D. Boscia⁴ and V. Pallás². ¹Certis Europe B.V., Via Guaragna 3, 21047 Saronno (VA), Italy. ²Instituto de Biología Molecular y Celular de Plantas, Universidad Politécnica, CSIC, Avenida de los Naranjos s/n 46022 Valencia, Spain. ³Dipartimento di Protezione delle Piante e Microbiologia Applicata, Università degli Studi, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. ⁴Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, Unità Organizzativa di Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. E-mail: d.boscia@ba.ivr.cnr.it

American plum line pattern virus (APLPV), a member of the genus *Illarvirus* thought for long time to occur only in North America, was recorded during the last few years in isolated trees/foci from several Mediterranean countries in Japanese plum and sweet cherry. Line pattern symptoms were observed during spring 2009 in some flowering cherries (*P. serrulata*) in Northern Italy (Piedmont and Lombardia). A total of 22 trees (symptomatic and symptomless) were sampled randomly from seven locations: Verbania, Saronno, Rovellasca, Rovello Porro, Cantù, Bregnano and Solaro. All sampled trees were ELISA-tested for the following viruses: *Plum pox virus* (PPV), *Prunus necrotic ringspot virus* (PNRSV), *Prune dwarf virus* (PDV), *Apple mosaic virus* (ApMV), *Apple chlorotic leafspot virus* (ACLSV) and APLPV. The same samples were tested by molecular hybridization (poly and virus-specific probes) and by RT-PCR (simultaneous and virus-specific) for the same viruses and for *Apricot latent virus* (ApLV), *Plum bark necrosis stem pitting-associated virus* (PBNSPaV), *Peach latent mosaic viroid* (PLMVd) and *Hop stunt viroid* (HSVd). Two samples were positive for APLPV and four for

PDV, including one mixed infections. APLPV-positive samples were found in Verbania. Sequence analysis of a PCR amplicon confirmed the presence of this virus. To our knowledge, this is the first report of APLPV in flowering cherry in Italy. However, more extensive studies are needed to check the virus status of ornamental nurseries, to evaluate virus incidence in the territory, and the potential risks of transmission to cultivated stone fruits.

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF PEACH AND GRAPE DEFENSINS DIFFERENTIALLY EXPRESSED DURING FRUIT RIPENING. V. Nanni¹, E. Baraldi¹, M. Bellucci² and P. Bertolini¹. ¹CRIOF, Dipartimento di Protezione e Valorizzazione Agroalimentare, Laboratorio di Biotecnologie, Università degli Studi, Viale Fanin 46, 40127 Bologna, Italy. ²Dipartimento di Scienze e Tecnologie Agroambientali, Laboratorio di Chimica Bioinorganica, Università degli Studi, Viale Fanin 46, 40127 Bologna, Italy. E-mail: elena.baraldi@unibo.it

Plant defensins are a large family of small, cationic, cysteine-rich peptides playing a crucial role in plant innate immunity. Because of their known antimicrobial activity against important plant pathogens, plant defensins are very interesting targets for agrobiotechnology applications. In this study we show that defensin genes from peach (*Prunus persica*) and grape (*Vitis vinifera*) are highly expressed at different stages of fruit ripening. In peach fruits, the defensin transcript level drastically decreases from the early (S1 and S2) to the late (S3, S4) stages of ripening, whereas, in grape, defensin expression increases at veraison and remains stable afterwards. Two recombinant defensins were expressed in *E. coli* and purified to homogeneity. The recombinant proteins were tested for their antimicrobial activity against important fungal pathogens and human and plant bacterial pathogens. Both specifically inhibited the germination of *Penicillium expansum* and *Botrytis cinerea* while peach defensin inhibited also the germination of *Monilia laxa*. Furthermore, in accordance with other plant defensins, both defensins did not show antibacterial activity against plant and human pathogens.

IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF POTATO SPINDLE TUBER VIROID INFECTING TOMATO IN ITALY. B. Navarro¹, M.R. Silletti², V.N. Trisciuzzi² and F. Di Serio¹. ¹Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, Unità Organizzativa di Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²Centro di Ricerca e Sperimentazione in Agricoltura Basile Caramia, Via Cisternino 281, 70010 Locorotondo (BA), Italy. E-mail: f.diserio@ba.ivr.cnr.it

Potato spindle tuber viroid (PSTVd), a quarantine plant pathogen in Europe, has been detected in tomato plants in northern Italy. Infected plants, showing shortened internodes, deformed and necrotic leaves, and abnormal fruit maturation, were found close to symptomless *Solanum jasminoides* plants also infected by PSTVd. Molecular characterization of field isolates, biological assays with viroidal cDNA infectious clones and sequence analyses of the resulting progenies support the possibility of PSTVd transmission to tomato plants from the neighbouring infected *S. jasminoides* plants. This is the first report of tomato plants infected by PSTVd in Italy and the first well-supported evidence on the risk of PSTVd epidemic spread from symptomless ornamental *Solanaceae* to susceptible horticultural crops when prophylactic measures are not enforced. These results also suggest that occasional PSTVd outbreaks in tomato crops reported in several European countries in the last two decades could have a similar origin.

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